

Chemical Investigation of the Flowers of *Opuntia elatior* (Cactaceae)

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Air dried flowers of the plant (1 kg.) were extracted thrice with hot ethanol and the extract was concentrated and diluted with water. The aqueous extract, after the removal of fatty material with ether, was kept in a refrigerator for a fortnight when it deposited fine yellow crystals of a glycoside, m.p. 180-82° (4.8 gm). The glycoside gave positive colour reactions for flavones, and paper chromatography using butanol, acetic acid, water (4:1:1) showed it to be a single entity.

The glycoside was hydrolysed with 7% methanolic sulphuric acid for two hours and the yellow solid which separated out was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 302-305°, methyl ether, m.p. 150-52° and acetate m.p. 208-209°. The nature of the aglycone as isorhamnetin suggested by the above melting points was confirmed by comparison of the acetate with an authentic specimen of isorhamnetic acetate¹.

The location of the sugar in position 3 was established by methylation of the glycoside with dimethyl sulphate, in dry acetone over anhydrous potassium carbonate followed by hydrolysis with 7% methanolic sulphuric acid, which gave fine yellow needles, m.p. 198°. The hydrolysed product gave no depression in m.m.p. with an authentic sample of 5, 7, 3', 4' tetramethyl quercetin². The aqueous hydrolysate on evaporation to dryness under vacuum was shown to contain glucose and rhamnose by paper chromatography (butanol-water).

The glycoside was thus shown to be narcissin³.

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